

The first record of *Adrama apicalis* Shiraki from Hainan, with notes on its behavior

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A male of the fruit fly *Adrama apicalis* Shiraki, 1933, previously known to occur in Taiwan and Yunnan Provinces and infesting seeds of the tea (*Camellia sinensis* Kuntze) (Wang, X.-J. 1998. *The fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) of the East Asian Region. Acta Zootaxonomica Sinica* (1996), 21 (supplement)) was found and photographed near Tien Tze (=Tianchi) of Jian Feng Ling Nature Reserve of Hainan, China (ca. 18°44' N 108°51' E, h=820 m) on 21.04.2011 by To Chan and identified by VAK based on the series of photographs (Figs. 1–4) primarily presented at www.diptera.info. The specimen has widely black occiput and tergites 4 and 5, as well as the mesal crossband reaching only M vein. The male on the photographs strongly extends its abdominal pleura and holds abdomen up at the angle 45° apparently for dispersion of pheromones (in most tephritids, male sexual pheromones are produced by an anal gland and apparently are dispersed over pleura by means of the hind tarsi. Such an extension of male pleura has been already known in the subfamily Tephritinae (*Tephritis*, *Terellia*, *Chaetorellia*), but is recorded in the tribe Adramini (subfamily Trypetinae) for the first time.

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